

LOST IN CHAOS: NEW THINKING ON BRANDING A DRINKABLE CULTURE

A STUDY OF PU-ERH TEA – FROM THE 2007 BUBBLE BURST TO A PROPOSED EMOTIONAL BRAND DESIGN APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Pu-erh tea is referred as a “drinkable culture”. With a long history full of stories, Pu-erh tea is now more of an emotional product than a beverage. Emerged in 1999, and reached to its peak in 2007, a Pu-erh tea bubble burst, caused the collapse of the China tea market. The incident had led to subsequences of chaos in branding Pu-erh tea - irresponsible marketing concepts sprung up raiding the market which already lacking of quality-evaluation and monitoring mechanisms. The emotional connections between the consumers and the tea had been replaced by mistrust.

This on-going study of emotional brand design approach for Pu-erh tea is aiming at sorting out the mistaken ideas activating in the chaos and mapping out opportunities to allow new thinking in branding Pu-erh tea. A culture based emotional brand design approach is introduced in this paper and to be examined through real-world projects for further research.

Keywords: Chinese Culture, Ethnic Heritage, Affection, Emotional Branding Approach, Experience Design

INTRODUCTION: THE CHAOS

Pu-erh tea, a post-fermented tea, usually compared with Bordeaux and referred as “a drinkable culture” for its unique feature of requiring storing and aging for improving the quality of taste, is a healthy tea drink advocated in Chinese tea culture for it possess many

health benefits such as reducing cholesterol, an aid to digestion, nourishing stomach, etc., without affecting one’s sleep as the ripe tea contains less caffeine comparing to other teas. (Xu, X., Yan, M. and Zhu, Y., 2005)

In addition to the biological features, Pu-erh tea carries rich stories through its long history, creates multi-level culture based emotional bonds with its appreciators. The preference of Pu-erh tea over other types of traditional Chinese teas is usually based on the emotional experience a drinker can achieve through the tea-selecting, tea-storing, tea-making processes, and the spiritual gratification gained by imaging the scenarios of the stories attached to the tea, as well as knowing and feeling the body’s getting healthier while drinking the tea, rather than being fond of the flavors and tastes of this type of tea. Pu-erh tea, as it were, more of a kind of emotional goods, rather than simply a healthy beverage.

However, the 2007 bubble burst nearly cut off the emotional ties between the consumers and the tea. The positive emotional connections have been replaced by confusion, mistrust, and disappointment.

Began around 1999, the marketing focus of Pu-erh tea emphasized on promoting the concepts that “wild ancient tree Pu-erh” in every respect is superior to “cultivated bush Pu-erh”, making the scarcity of resources as the basis for price speculation. Pu-erh tea was positioned targeting the high-end consumer market, the price of the tea increased along ever since.

Moreover, as the tea can be optimized the taste after certain years of proper storage, it was put in oversimplified comparisons with Bordeaux and Maotai – a Chinese liquor, claiming that Pu-erh tea, as well is a good investment choice for the aging of the tea is proportional to its price, without taking into account the brands, the storage qualities, or any other contributing factors, in this portrayed value appreciation theory. As more and more tea merchants and individual tea collectors took in the theory of “better to save Pu-erh than to save money”, from 1999 to 2007, “the price of the tea, increased tenfold, to a high of \$150 a pound for the finest aged Pu-erh, before tumbling far below its pre-boom levels” (Jacobs, A., 2009). In 2007 May, the long-lasting bubble finally burst, the price of the tea dropped up to 50% (Lan, L.W., 2011). Until the start of this on-going study, some merchants of individual collectors have yet to recover the loss caused by the stocking up of Pu-erh tea. Private investors, businesses, tea farmers, as well as the government had become the victims of this Pu-erh tea chaos.

Some claimed to be antique Pu-erh tea cakes were put on auctions, exploiting the historical stories as the selling point, the auction price of “royal-court Pu-erh” once reached \$20,000 per 100 gram (Hanshan Normal University, 2010). But with the dubious authenticity of the auctioned tea, the history and culture of Pu-erh tea had been used only as tools for pursuing premium price, the emotional bonds created by them are no long considered. Stories were made up, concepts were concocted, plus numerous exaggerated promotional activities, all together intensified the degree of the Pu-erh tea market chaos. After the bubble collapsed, the excessive speculative marketing concepts were left in the market, people can no longer judge the quality, nor the accordingly appropriate price of Pu-erh tea, based on their “knowledge” of the tea implanted by the series of commercial practices. From individual Pu-erh Tea brands to Yunnan’s region’s brand of tea were all seriously damaged. “Lured by the quick profit temptation during the Pu-erh tea bubble, counties in Yunnan province invested in numerous small tea factories, more than 500 new factories were established in one of the counties” (Ye, Y., 2011). Due to the lacking of brand building, hundreds of small

businesses become tools of making quick profit during the boom, but after the bubble burst, for survival in the sluggish market, and in order to recoup their losses, they continue to decay the market and to overdraw the emotional brand assets of Pu-erh tea.

“During the boom, Pu-erh teas were made for quantity rather than quality, simply to fulfill the increase in orders, and new traders entered the market without any experience of Pu-erh trading. Their sole aim was to make quick money! They bought teas that they didn’t understand and certainly hadn’t tasted or even seen before buying” (Pettigrew, J., 2009). Based on the concepts of “wild ancient tree Pu-erh” is more valuable, and in the absence of monitoring and evaluating systems in the chaotic market, instead of building the brands of their own, low quality tea cakes were mass-produced by tea merchants and packaged with “wild ancient tree” marks. The similar attempts to promote one common concept instead of branding individual brands include the current popular one of “the six major tea mountain Pu-erh”, which will be discussed in the later section. This type of deliberately misleading branding attempts although seems to be an active branding approach, in fact not only contributing nothing to a beneficial market competition between brands, but also causing the retrogression of the brand building of the Pu-erh tea industry since it fully left out the emotional factors.

Having enumerated the consequences caused by the chaos, surprisingly, there are researches and statistics show that there’s no certain signs of structural downturn of the traditional tea sales over the years after the Pu-erh tea bubble burst. An important reason is that the traditional Chinese tea culture has been much accounted of the tea consumers nowadays (Wu, J, 2009), to fulfill the corresponding spontaneous emotional demands. Which is indicating an emotional brand design opportunity to genuinely reunited with the Pu-erh tea culture in order to accelerating the industry recovery.

BEFORE THE CHAOS: PU-ERH TEA CULTURE AND THE EMOTIONS

As an essential part of Chinese lifestyle, the profound tea culture is closely related with the concepts of Confucianism, Taoism and Buddhism, as the saying of “Tea and Zen share the same taste, Tea pot and Buddhism are an organic unity” implies. Environment of the tea ceremony ought to be elegant and quiet, allowing people to be enchanted during the tasting and the appreciation of the process. Through feeling and experiencing the making and drinking tea, emotional bonds are consolidated between people and tea. “Chinese tea represents a spiritual cultivation and cultural continuity, and the tea itself serves as a medium that changes direct relationships – from form to content, from material to spirit, between people and things – into interpersonal relationships, as found in traditional China culture. The spiritual essence of tea in Chinese culture thus constitutes a significant portion of the brand positions and advertising that attempt to prompt consumers to attach emotion and spirituality to their buying behavior” (Lee, C.W., Liao, C.S. 2009). Culture and emotion are the two essential elements to the branding strategies of Chinese tea. And Pu-erh tea, in specific, has its own unique cultural background and profound emotional bonding with its consumers.

A ETHNIC HERITAGE

Pu-erh tea was originated in several specific counties in southern Yunnan province of China, included Xishuangbanna, Simao and Lincang areas, mainly cultivated by the ethnic groups of “Bu Lang”, “Wa”, “Ji Nuo”, “De Ang”, “Ha Ni” and “Dai” living in those areas and constituted an important part of their daily diet. The recorded history of Pu-erh tea can be traced back to some 1,700 years ago according to the historical documents. (Ahmed, S., Unachukwu, U., Stepp, J.R., Peters, C.M., Long, C.L., Kennelly, E., 2010)

Pu-erh tea itself shares the same qualities with these ethnic group people: simple but dynamic, restrained but sincere, straightforward yet mysterious, with a vintage taste. The aroma of Pu-erh is not as strong as other Chinese tea, the taste of it is rather moderate but continuously changing over time and storage conditions, it contains low-level of caffeine, it brings a soothing feeling rather than stimulations.

When people consume Pu-erh tea, they will experience emotional connections generated by these ethnic characteristics.

A DRINKABLE CULTURE

The tea is named after the town called “Pu-erh”, which once was the distributing center of the “Ancient Tea-and-Horse Route” appeared since Tang Dynasty. And the processing history of Pu-erh tea can be dated back to the East Han Dynasty over 1,700 years ago. Pu-erh tea was carried into Tibet through the “Ancient Tea-and-Horse Route” and became a daily necessity to provide nutrition and vitamins to the nomadic people. And later it became the “tribute tea” to the royals in Qing Dynasty. The long history endowed Pu-erh tea a rich cultural background.

Since Pu-erh tea is dynamic as the flavor and the color of it changes over time, it is common to storage the tea over decades to experience the changing process, or simply for pursuing a better ripe taste. Therefore there’s the saying of “Grandfather makes the tea, Grandson sells the tea” to point out this unique feature of Pu-erh tea. Pu-erh tea is perceived as a type of tea that each cake of them carries stories throughout the making and storage process.

Comparing to other tea types, Pu-erh tea is not about the fragrance but the flavor, which is blended with the taste of its culture background, affect and emotions generated by its history and stories. Pu-erh tea is referred as a “drinkable culture”, and the spiritual essence of drinking Pu-erh tea is to drink the “white space” of it, just like the artistic conceptions of Chinese painting.

A PIECE OF ART

Given that people emphasize more on the spiritual essence of Pu-erh tea and its unique feature of being able to be collected and stored. Pu-erh tea is also considered as a piece of art. Embossing of traditional patterns, historical stories, or monumental designs that line with Chinese aesthetics is a common practice in making the Pu-erh tea cakes.

Figure 1. Pu-erh tea cake with Chinese Zodiac Design. (Photography / Cai Cong Ting) Image source: http://tea.tw.tranews.com/Show/Style7/News/c1_News.asp?SItemId=0271030&ProgramNo=a400022000001&SubjectNo=3230043

THE STUDY

THE OBJECTIVES AND THE METHOD

To look into the in-depth relationships between the Pu-erh tea culture and its consumers' corresponding emotions toward it, in order to identify and understand the effective emotions for mapping out the emotional branding opportunities of the Pu-erh tea industry, an on-going study were started in June 2011. The by far stages of this study were conducted in qualitative methods through field research in Yunnan province, China, visiting major tea markets, minority commodity fairs and major tea brand retails. In-depth interviews with four Yunnan University professors, from both the anthroposociology and design aspects, the author of "Theory on Chinese Tea: Art and Culture" (Yang, K. N., 2006), and local (ethnic and Han) tea brand owners. Participant observation and semi-structured interviews were conducted with local and non-local consumers in Pu-erh tea tasting and consuming environments. The findings and analysis of the up to now study are presented as follow.

THE FINDINGS

The storage life of Pu-erh tea

Although there's no conclusive scientific data shows whether there's a upper limit to Pu-erh tea's storage life, nor how many years of storage should it take to develop the best of its flavor, summed up by experienced Pu-erh tea merchants and tea consumers, under the premise of the proper storage conditions, and depends on the quality of raw

material, roughly unified data were able to be collected and listed as below. In general, the quality of the taste would decline after the peak year. Which disproves the fabricated feature of Pu-erh tea being "the older the better".

	Pre-sale Storage	Flavor Peak
Raw Pu-erh	2-3 years	20-30 years
Ripe Pu-erh	8-10 years	30-50 years

Figure 2. The storage life of Pu-erh tea.

The altered Pu-erh tea culture and the branding approach

The speculators fully made use of the Pu-erh tea culture, as they realize without exploiting the contents of the Pu-erh tea culture, the validity of the speculations would be questioned, and the endurance of the effect would be compromised. So numerous claimed-to-be tea experts appeared everywhere in the market to preach Pu-erh tea culture, through founding Pu-erh tea institutes, publications, and professional look-and-feel web sites. Only the contents were altered when needed to coordinate with the marketing and business demands (Ye, Y., 2011). Instead of undertaking the responsibility to rebuild the standard system of Pu-erh tea industry in order to aid the consumers in better understanding the tea, nor considering the genuine emotions the consumers pursuing from Pu-erh tea, they are pulling the already chaotic market to a further level of deterioration. "Form follows function", when the whole industry is solely after profit, the employed branding approaches follow the misleading function. The chaos of the industry leads to the chaos in branding Pu-erh tea in the post-bubble burst years.

THE CHAOS IN BRANDING PU-ERH TEA

The most obvious and serious disturbance generated by the chaos is the endless concocted marketing concepts either for recouping the losses or simply for pursuing short-term profits. These false concepts of Pu-erh tea caused confusions for consumers and irresponsible dealers, some baseless assertions even spread out trough professional articles and books, not only holding back the reconstruction of the chaotic tea market after the bubble burst, but also damaging the reputation of the overall Pu-erh tea brand, resulting Pu-erh tea lost its true emotional essence, became a

tea commonly referred and quoted as “the tea you can’t understand even if you study it your whole life”. Chart below collects the commonly used inauthentic concepts still activating in the market during this ongoing study through literature review, field research interviews and participant observations. The concepts are listed in an order from the most destructive to less harmful, and the most obstructing ones will be briefly discussed in this section.

The Inauthentic Marketing Concepts

<i>“The older the better”</i>	The tea flavor is enhanced through aging. The quality and the price rest with the age of the tea.
<i>“Drinkable Antique”</i>	Emphasis on the history of some age-old tea, proposed a “tasteless taste” concept.
<i>“A good investment choice”</i>	Like wine, Pu-erh tea’s value increase by years, it’s a good investment choice for tea lovers and collectors.
<i>“Wild ancient tree Pu-erh is better than the cultivated bush Pu-erh”</i>	The theory claimed that the best and most valuable Pu-erh tea is made of wild ancient tree leaves over a thousand years old. And in general “tree Pu-erh” is better than “bush Pu-erh”.
<i>“Pu-erh tea from certain mountains is better than others”</i>	There are “6 ancient Pu-erh mountains” and “6 new Pu-erh mountains”, Pu-erh tea are commonly named and branded by mountains currently in the market.
<i>“Pu-erh tea cake made of single batch of leaves is better than the blend ones”</i>	Selling point emphasis on one Pu-erh tea cake is made of single batch of leaves, overthrow the traditional practice of cakes made of mixed and matched batches of leaves.
<i>“Raw Pu-erh is better than ripe Pu-erh”</i>	Collectors should invest on the unfermented raw tea. Microbial fermented ripe tea could be mass-produced therefore should be low-cost with no investment value.
<i>“Dry storage is better than wet storage”</i>	Dry storage is the process of natural aging through autoxidation. Wet storage is the microbial fermentation or artificial fermentation. Dry storage takes longer than wet storage to reach certain quality of the tea therefore it’s better than wet storage.

<i>“Non storage is even better”</i>	Collectors are encouraged to buy in raw Pu-erh tea that has never been storage in any kind of warehouses, and create an autoxidation environment for aging the tea at home. Claiming this decrease the possibility for the tea to get moldy, and increase the reserve value.
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“The older the better”

Many of the inauthentic concepts were cooked up base on this commonly employed idea of “the older the better”, simply misleading the consumers to believe that the age of the tea is proportional to the quality and therefore the price of the tea, without giving a scientifically rational time limit to the years of age, which even lead to the pursuing of the “tasteless taste” realm which again, exploited by marketing needs solely for pursuing premium price without taking into account that untruthful concepts would harm the feelings and emotion bonds of the consumers. Despite the scientific fact that even some Pu-erh tea cakes could maintain a tasteful flavor after several decades, once the tea reached the peak year (see Figure 2.) of quality under the premise of proper storage conditions, the taste would decline thereafter, which is determined by the law of nature.

“Wild ancient tree Pu-erh from certain mountains is better than others”

Ever since the “six new Pu-erh tea mountains” become a declared concept in corresponding to the “six ancient Pu-erh tea mountains”, the names of the new mountains in a way became the brands of Pu-erh tea, same as the way that almost every tea cake in the market is branded as “wild ancient tree Pu-erh” in order to raise the price. Instead of building individual retail brands, tea shops emphasis on publicizing the concepts of mountains (Wu, J, 2009). During the peak of the Pu-erh tea boom, almost every tourists went to Yunnan would leave with several “mountain branded wild ancient tree Pu-erh”. But according to statistical data in Ye, Y.’s article (2011), by current definition of “ancient Pu-erh tree” approved on the 2005 International Symposium of Ancient Pu-erh Tea Mountains, which include semi-cultivated wild tea trees and artificial-cultivated tea trees over one hundred years, the maximum annual production of 50 yards of “ancient Pu-erh tree” is no more than 100kg.

It is simply impossible that Yunnan province's annual output of the "mountain branded wild ancient tree Pu-erh" is capable to cope up with the number of sales. The consequences of this type of branding approaches instead of building retail brands, will only overdraw the overall Pu-erh tea's emotional brand assests, weakening the competitiveness of the whole industry.

"Raw Pu-erh is better than ripe Pu-erh"

The idea of "Raw Pu-erh is better than ripe Pu-erh" is based on the strategy of positioning Pu-erh tea as financial products, rather than spiritual consumer goods, as it were. The real intension behind the attempt to temper the property of Pu-erh tea is to prepare for the theory of Pu-erh tea is "a good investment choice" which again, linked back to the idea of "the older the better". But the fact is, once Pu-erh tea lost its intrinsic property as an emotional and health beneficial beverage, the advantages of Pu-erh tea comparing to other types of teas are significantly weakened. By intentionally depreciating the "ripe Pu-erh" in order to promote the "raw Pu-erh", the industry is sabotaging the foundation of itself, as well as the region's brand of Pu-erh tea.

CULTURE BASED EMOTIONAL BRAND DESIGN APPROACH

Before going into more in-depth discussion of how to map out opportunities for developing new thinking in branding Pu-erh tea, this section will explain the culture based emotional brand design approach developed during this in progress study, which is to be examined through real-world projects for further research in later stages of the study.

The conventional version of definition of a brand as a "name, term design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller's good or service as distinct from those of other sellers" provided by the American Marketing Association clearly does not fit for the rapid development of the discipline as well as people's cognition any more. Instead, a more compendious definition that keeps up with the evolvment defines a brand or branding as "it allows a company to differentiate themselves from the competition and, in the process, to bond with their customers to create

loyalty" (Webster, K. K., 2002) And for a brand to bond with its customers, it is to be equally equipped with intellectual depth that is able to psychologically generate and trigger proper emotions of the customers. The intellectual depth needed here, is culture.

This has been backed up by evidences of the branding strategies gradually transformed from conventional into emotional. The emphases on surface feature designs are shifted to understand the inner core of culture and emotions relationships that are supporting and endowing meaning to the outer features.

This is why the culture based emotional brand design research study is in demand, especially for the rapid economic developing China market, to prevent further damage on the already existing chaos of irrational brand designs as the consequences of the pursuit of quick profit. The emphasis of brand design, should be accordingly shifted from featural to emotional, as well the new focus of the outcome should be on multi-sensory experiences, rather than simply the visual designs.

THE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE RELATIONS BETWEEN CULTURE, EMOTION AND BRAND DESIGN

An initial conceptual framework was developed at the current stage of the study base on literatures reviewed up to date and the framework is to be examined and refined as the study progress.

This initial conceptual framework clearly shows the relationships between culture, emotion and design in branding. As well as how the three act on generating business value including both profit and benefit aspects, instead of the current common brand design practices weighting too much on commercial-value-driven strategies which actually a backward derivation in reverse to the actual psychological process of consumer behavior. Understanding the emotions that drive brand purchase in order to obtain the deserved business value corresponding to the effective emotions and quality time invested is the key.

Figure 3: Full Version of the Conceptual Framework

For a clearer view, as the simplified version of the conceptual framework shown below, the two critical parameters in brand design are “emotion” and “time”, more precisely, “effective emotion” and “quality time”. “Value” here in specific for “commercial value” is only a result, not a contributing parameter to the process. It doesn’t matter whether the “value” that has been valued and desired is “profit” or “benefit”. They come afterwards depending on the emotions and time have been invested and successfully embedded into the product. The other uncertain and indecisive variables are eliminated in this context. And “time” could be decreased by other means depends on contexts, “technology” for instance. And in the case for Pu-erh tea, it could be proper “fermentation method” and “storage conditions”. This conceptual framework shows that “emotion” stands in the center role of the relation between culture, emotion and brand design. “Emotion” also acts the key factor of successful brand design in generating value. And encoding the proper emotions, which could be effectively decoded as desired, is the state we want to achieve.

Figure 4: Simplified Version of the Conceptual Framework

As for culture, the cultural factors are sometimes considered as barriers to effective communication, but here we consider it as opportunities to better understand emotions thoroughly in order to provide traces in discovering how emotions affect consumer

behavior for a particular group of people sharing the similar culture background.

Therefore, base on the proposed framework, we can sort out the proper order and logic in developing an emotional brand design approach for branding Pu-erh tea. As discussed above, Pu-erh tea carries rich culture and stories, and solid emotional foundation, which is Pu-erh tea’s true essence, formed through out its long history. Pu-erh tea is fully equipped with the two most critical factors of “emotion” and “time”, as long as genuine and spontaneous emotional factors are properly utilized, the “value” of both “profit” and “benefit” will be legitimately realized.

NEW THINKING ON PU-ERH TEA BRANDING

By far this on-going study is at the stage of mapping out the opportunities to develop new thinking in branding Pu-erh tea through an emotional brand design approach. In this section, a few initial considerations are discussed for further and indepth development as the study progress.

THE ESSENCE OF PU-ERH TEA: A DRINKABLE CULTURE, BUT STILL A DRINK

As discussed in earlier section, Pu-erh tea is commonly referred as “a drinkable culture” in commercial practices. As a positioning it is rather understandable and nothing wrong. But if we solely stress the role of culture, no longer consider its nature as a drink that is tied with multi-level of emotions, we would lose the foundation of the Pu-erh tea of branding. “At a high price, with the concept of Pu-erh tea as a good investment choice, and using ‘culture’ as the tool for speculations, Pu-erh tea had become a symbol of identity, social status, even religion” (Ye, Y., 2011). Instead of considered as an emotional consumer goods, Pu-erh tea is more integrated into the characteristics of financial products for investment purposes.

It is time we return to the essential attribute of Pu-erh tea as a drink attached with daily and close to life emotions, and reconsider the positioning focus when collaborating its cultural background. For example, as a drink, Pu-erh tea has a distinctive flavor of being mild, which is aligned with the emotional demand of

pursuing moderated lifestyle of the Pu-erh tea consumers. The idea of Pu-erh tea representing the well-being stage of life, can be linked with the taste of the tea, and conveyed when the consumer is drinking it, thus, generating the desired emotional bonding between the consumers and the tea, in order to strengthen the brand images.

STORYTELLING

Given that Pu-erh tea is a type of tea that has long histories and full of stories, telling brand story in a proper way can be a good opportunity for enhancing the brand cognition degrees as well as the competitive strengths. But instead of the current practices of fabricating stories to individual tea cakes, the brand storytelling can be considered to employ a style of being spiritual that contributes to its emotion arousing, and the subject of the stories can be Pu-erh tea in general. For example, as the Pu-erh tea consumers value the artistic concept of “serendipity – a good tea cake can only be obtained by luck, but not through seeking”, well told stories on this topic stands a good chance to contribute the brand building.

EMOTIONAL TOUCH POINT MAP & EXPERIENCE DESIGN

The typical retail trading process of Pu-erh tea is different from other types of tea, for the quality of Pu-erh tea can only be told through tasting by the consumers before they purchase. So it's common practice that in typical Pu-erh tea retails, consumers would be invited to sit down with the shop assistants, taste different types and years of Pu-erh tea, be enquired preferences, learn Pu-erh tea from the shop assistants, before making any purchases. Although there's no standard Pu-erh tea ceremony, but its unique way of selling, has already become a part of Pu-erh tea consuming culture itself. Which provides the opportunities to draw out an emotional touch point map throughout the retail purchasing process, in order to develop experience designs accordingly to create a unified brand atmosphere.

Figure 4: Pu-erh tea tasting in retail. Image source: <http://cahsz1951.blog.163.com/blog/static/104264315201172155742139/>

Further research is required for mapping out specific valid emotional effecting on each emotional touch point, by understanding the full-scale functions of the sites, as well as possible emotional experience scenarios different segments of consumers may encounter. Methods of experimental touch point scenario reproduction, combined with observation, interviews and focus groups can be employed. Study and analyze the behaviors reflected emotion responses and the descriptive emotion responses of the observed participants and interviewees are equally crucial.

Only by understanding the corresponding emotions that are resonated with the consumer base on the Pu-erh tea culture, and design the emotional touch point experiences accordingly, that way can we develop specific and effective branding approaches for promoting the Pu-erh tea industry.

CONCLUSION AND FURTHER STUDY

It's been over four years after the Pu-erh tea bubble burst when this on-going study started in June 2011, the whole industry was still suffering from the remaining issues and struggling to recover from the chaotic situation. This study was carried out aiming at sorting out the remaining inauthentic marketing concepts activating in the market which are overdrawing the overall Pu-erh tea brand and its emotional assets, as a foundational first step for further developing an emotional brand design approach, looking at mapping out opportunities in developing new thinking in branding Pu-erh tea for the future.

REMAINING QUESTIONS

As the on-going study is at the stage of developing the culture based emotional branding approach, below are several remaining crucial questions to be accounted in and answered in next steps of the study:

Different cultural backgrounds

In the practices of branding representative product of one culture to another, how to measure and manage the matching level of emotions embedded by the designers / producers and the desired emotions of consumers with different cultural backgrounds? In the case of Pu-erh tea, the cultural differences would be between the ethnic cultures and the mainstream cultures of the consumer markets.

The “Xenophilia” Phenomenon

There are phenomenal evidences shown in consumer behaviors in China that people tend to be more attracted to products based on ‘foreign’ cultures, the emotional factors of this phenomenon are crucial in the study of branding Pu-erh tea to a wider market which is not sharing the same culture origins.

The segmentation consideration

The current common practices of customer segmentation in branding are still tend to base on the physical attributes of similarities such as “income-level, education-level, social status, occupation, age and gender”, etc. Mood boards would then be developed for in-depth understanding of the selected target audience in those relatively comprehensive and preferable practices. But according to the above discussion and the proposed conceptual framework, a demand tendency to switch the order for customer segmentation has emerged. It seems to be more reasonable to first segment emotional attributes base on different cultural backgrounds, targeting the desired group that has certain level of potential to be

aroused emotional resonance with the culture based emotional attributes encoded to the brand. Only after the psychological group has been defined, in-depth segmentations of the physical attributes shall be conducted and aiding the product-line positioning and product cost designs. An in-depth demonstrative study of this thinking should be considered in future research for developing practicable and preferable emotional branding strategies.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, S., Unachukwu, U., Stepp, J.R., Peters, C.M., Long, C.L., Knelly, E. (2010), *Pu-erh tea tasting in Yunnan, China: Correlation of drinkers' perceptions to phytochemistry*, Journal of Ethnopharmacology, Volume 132, Issue 1, 28 October 2010, Pages 176-185, ISSN 0378-8741, 10.1016/j.jep.2010.08.016.
- Hanshan Normal University. (2010), *Introduction of Yunnan Pu-erh Tea*, Foreign Language Department Newsletter, 15 June
- Jacobs, A. (2009), *A County in China Sees Its Fortunes in Tea Leaves Until a Bubble Bursts*. The New York Times, 17 January
- Lan, L.W. (2011), *The Mystery of the Pu-erh Tea Bubble*, Public Financial Advisor, 25 October
- Lee, C.W., Liao, C.S. (2009) *The effects of consumer preferences and perceptions of Chinese tea beverages on brand positioning strategies*, British Food Journal, Vol. 111 Iss: 1, pp.80 – 96
- Norman, D.A. (2004). *Emotional design: why we love (or hate) everyday things*, New York: Basic Books, c2004.
- Pettigrew, J. (2009), *Pu-erh Tea Bulls and Bears*, Tea and Coffee Asia, 11 December <http://www.teacoffeeasia.com/categoryblog/177-puerh-tea-bulls-and-bears.html>, 7 February 2012
- Webster, K.K. (2002), *The definition of branding*, 21 October, http://www.marketingvox.com/the_definition_of_branding-011611/ 7 February 2012
- Wu, J. (2009), *Pu-erh Tea Marketing*, Yunnan Fine Arts Publishing House, Yunnan Publishing Group
- Xu, X., Yan, M. and Zhu, Y. (2005), *Influence of Fungal Fermentation on the Development of Volatile Compounds in the Puer Tea Manufacturing Process*. Engineering in Life Sciences, 5: 382–386. doi: 10.1002/elsc.200520083
- Yang, K. N., (2006), *Theory on Chinese Tea: Art and Culture*, Yunnan Education Publishing House
- Ye, Y. (2011), *The Inside Story of the 2007 Pu-erh Tea Speculation*. Yunnan Tea Network, 23 December, <http://www.51zm.cn/html/gongsixinwen/231.html>, 7 February 2012